

iOBS deliverables 2.1 and 2.2: Introduction to the development of quality control methods

Main project: Improved Observation Usage in NWP (iOBS), 2019-2021

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Work Package 2 (WP2): Machine learning QC algorithms of conventional observations

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The purpose of the work package 2 (WP2) was to develop/pilot adaptive statistical and machine learning (ML) quality control (QC) methods to effectively qualify observation data of conventional and personal weather stations (CWS and PWS (here NetAtmo), respectively) for the data assimilation.

WP2 focused on four methods:

- Spatial pairwise method based on dynamic linear model to find drifting behaviour of the sensors, air temperature, studied for CWS network (Task 2.1)
- Statistical adaptive threshold method based on generalized extreme value function, air temperature, studied for CWS network (Task 2.2)
- Spatial consistency of NetAtmo stations with CWS network based on kriging method, studied for PWS network (Task 2.3)
- Spatial consistency between NetAtmo stations based on density-based clustering, studied for PWS network (Task 2.3)

Also random forest (RF) and nearest neighbour (NN) methods were tested but they were only used as additional examples and were not accurately optimized and documented.

In addition, preprocessing workflow of observational data was piloted in the Apache Airflow environment at the CSC and FMI. First, CSC built the preprocessing infrastructure based on Apache Airflow and runs it once per day for the NetAtmo observations. Based on the learnings from CSC, Apache Airflow environment is also tested at FMI to estimate if the tool is usable and integratable in FMI's environment. The Airflow piloting will be reported as part of the WP5 (deliverable 5.1) and by the end of May after studies at FMI are finished.

Task 2.1 Spatial QC analysis method

The motivation for spatial QC analysis method based on pairwise anomaly detection was on the long term drifting of air temperature values on an operative CWS recognized after some statistical analysis.

Within the project, the method was first developed for air temperature of the CWS network. Tests were also made on pressure data from the PWS network, but the short observational history was not long enough for the developed method. Thus, the project finally focused on developing the method for the air temperature observations.

The method is based on calculating pairwise differences between neighbouring stations, with the idea to decompose the difference time series into trend, cyclic and residual components (figure 1). The decomposition is made using dynamic linear models (DLM), which separately accounts for the trend and cyclic variations. After these components have been removed, the residual component is inspected for potential shifts in the time series by calculating so-called Hotelling statistics assuming that the pairwise differences follow a multivariate normal distribution. Quality control charts based on the Hotelling statistics are used to visually analyze and detect (in conjunction with some detection criteria) the potential shifts from the data (figure 2).

Figure 1. The difference time series decomposed into trend, cyclic and residual components using dynamic linear models.

Figure 2. Quality control charts based on the Hotelling statistics.

The tools to run the method are open access and are available here:

<https://source.coderefinery.org/iOBS/wp2/task2.1/dlmqc>

The detailed description and usage example of the method named DLMQC (Dynamic Linear Model Quality Control) is presented here:

<https://source.coderefinery.org/iOBS/wp2/task2.1/dlmqc/-/blob/master/vignettes/dlmqc-example.Rmd>

Task 2.2 Automatic adaptive range test

Daily maximum and minimum thresholds are assigned based on the history of a measurement station. The algorithm is based on the work by Hasu & Aaltonen (Automatic Minimum and Maximum Alarm Thresholds for Quality Control, Hasu, V & Aaltonen, A, 2010, Journal of atmospheric and oceanic technology). The mathematical basis of the algorithm is in generalized extreme-value function. For each day of the year, the data consists of the maximum and minimum measurements from the given day of each year in station history, plus adjacent days. The n days are weighted to account for the temporal distance. To this data the generalized extreme value function is fitted and the threshold is assigned to the decided quantile.

Because of the statistical character of the method, it is worth mentioning that the longer the observation history is, the more reliable are the created thresholds. There should be at least some years, rather more than 10 years, of observation history at a station to be reasonable to create the adaptive thresholds. In addition, method operability is dependent on how the observations in question are distributed (e.g. air temperature, air pressure, wind).

Observations can be checked against these thresholds point-by-point. It is reasonable to update the thresholds regularly, e.g. ones per year or monthly or on demand.

Within the project, the method was tested for air temperature and pressure observations. The studies showed that for the air pressure, the created thresholds didn't give much additional value when compared to the traditional ways of doing QC. Thus, the project finally focused on developing the method for the air temperature observations.

At FMI, an user interface to update minimum and maximum threshold station-specifically when needed was implemented within the project in addition to the updated version of the adaptive threshold method QC. An example of the created daily thresholds for a station with the observation history of 60 years (Helsinki Kaisaniemi) is shown in figure 3. The figure also shows frequency distributions of daily minimum and maximum temperatures for a certain day with the thresholds created by the method. The day to show the distribution can be chosen by the user. These figures are available in the user interface of FMI for each of the CWS observing air temperature.

Figure 3. daily minimum and maximum thresholds of a CWS (Helsinki Kaisaniemi) shown in FMI's user interface. The figure also shows minimum and maximum frequency distributions of a certain day (here 25.6.) with the thresholds created.

The tools to run the method are open access and are available here:

<https://source.coderefinery.org/iOBS/wp2/task-2.2/max-and-min-thresholds>

Task 2.3 Exploratory ML analysis of personal weather station (PWS) data

Usability of machine learning (ML) methods in quality assurance of a PWS network (NetAtmo) was investigated for air temperature and pressure observations. Detailed studies were built on two methods: spatial kriging and clustering. In addition, random forest (RF) and nearest neighbour (NN) methods were used as simple comparison examples especially for the kriging method but those were not in focus of the project and thus, not documented properly.

ML-methods were firstly developed to create a list of stations that fill the acceptance limits of the method in question. This means that the methods didn't check observations point-by-point but rather give a white list of stations for a certain period. After this station filtering, it would be recommended to use additional QC tests for observation qualification.

The ML methods include parameters that allow optimization of filtering efficiency of stations based on the user needs. If the high number of stations is preferred, the settings can be chosen to be looser keeping in mind the possible deterioration of the data quality. Tighter parameter settings might lead to a decreased amount of stations. Within the iOBS project, the method outcome was optimized to answer the needs of the data assimilation development of the project by adding an option to use thinning for the ML handled data.

Spatial consistency of PWS with conventional weather stations (CWS)

2D (longitude and latitude) kriging (also called Gaussian process interpolation) method was developed to do quality control of NetAtmo-PWS network. A set of conventional weather stations (CWSs) was used as a ground-truth for the interpolation. CWSs were chosen to represent the reference network because of their proven quality. However, the ground-truth data was only based on either air temperature or pressure data without any supporting information, such as meteorological or geographical information. Therefore, the interpolated field does not take into account small scale factors influenced by the environment. This means that interpolated values themselves are also an error source in the calculation in addition to the factors dependent on the PWS network. Within the project, the CWS was used as a first guess for the reference data set. Generally, the PWS and CWS datasets can be obtained from multiple sources and will be preprocessed into a common format in the first stage.

Based on the interpolation of CWS measurements, the method predicts the values of PWSs for every timestamp in some temporal range (i.e. the training phase). The interpolation shows some errors against the CWS observations because of e.g. noise in interpolation/measurement or systematic observations errors. Based on frequency and value thresholds for the errors set by the user, the method filters out the PWSs that have too often,

too high interpolation error. An underlying assumption in the developed method is that the measurements of a PWS should not systematically differ from the interpolated field over a relatively long period of time. An alternative approach would e.g. be to analyze the differences between neighboring PWSs and to identify the stations that produce anomalous measurements.

The idea of the developed method is shown in picture 4. There, the leftmost picture shows air temperatures of the CWS network in the Helsinki metropolitan area. The interpolation results based on CWS observations are shown in the middle picture and the error estimation of PWS stations based on the interpolation is shown on the rightmost picture. Here it has to be remembered that interpolation of the CWS observations does not take into account meteorological conditions or influence of placement of the station. Thus, the interpolation itself is already an error source.

As the last stage, the accepted stations can also be filtered with a spatial thinning method, where, within a certain-sized spatial grid, only the best PWS (i.e. the one with the lowest rejection rate) is kept. The use of thinning is optional to fit the various user needs.

Figure 4. Information needed and created by the developed kriging method are shown in the maps representing Helsinki metropolitan area: leftmost picture shows the network of CWS, the picture in the middle represents the interpolation of temperatures based on the CWS network and the rightmost picture shows the errors of NetAtmo stations created by the developed kriging method.

The tools to run the method are open access and are available here:

<https://source.coderefinery.org/iOBS/wp2/task-2-3/kriging>

Spatial and observation-space density-based clustering: Consistency between PWS observations

An unsupervised clustering method to find clusters of similar stations for quality control of observations collected from Netatmo PWS network was developed. Within a given assimilation window (DTG), similarity between stations is established via a custom distance matrix. The method defines set of DTGs to be analysed and, for each of them:

- Collects appropriate data (handle missing values, rm duplicates, etc)

- Calculates a generalised distance matrix (taking into account spatial coordinates and observation values) and pass it to a density-based clustering algorithm (e.g., HDBSCAN, DBSCAN, OPTICS)
- Removes outliers

After that, the results are analyzed from each DTG and lists of “accepted”, “rejected” and “spatially inconsistent” stations are generated.

As the last stage, the accepted stations can also be filtered with a spatial thinning method, where, within a certain-sized spatial grid, only the best PWS (i.e. the one with the lowest rejection rate) is kept. The use of thinning is optional to fit the various user needs.

The application to run the method is named as `netatmoqc` and is open access:

<https://source.coderefinery.org/iOBS/wp2/task-2-3/netatmoqc>

Performance analysis of the QC-methods of PWS data

The performance of some ML QC-methods tested within the project were evaluated by predicting CWS observations based on observations of accepted PWSs.

Aggregation of a total of six different regression methods with mean of the methods was used to produce the final measure of performance for the given QC-method (2D kriging, random forest, nearest neighbour). The mean prediction error describes the performance of a certain method. In principle, the smaller the error, the better is the performance of a method. Here the idea of performance evaluation is not to provide absolute estimates of the prediction errors but rather give an idea whether the used methods differ clearly from each other or not. Based on the results it can be concluded whether it is worth using a more complicated ML-method or if a simpler algorithm, e.g. random forest or nearest neighbour regression, would be acceptable.

As the CWSs were used both for training of the kriging QC method and for the evaluation of the QC-methods it was important to split the CWSs into the training and evaluation data sets. This was done by using MD5-hash-based station splitting.

In addition to the performance evaluation of mentioned ML-methods, a quality control software developed at Norwegian Meteorological Institute, [TITAN \(auTomatlc daTa quAlity coNtrol\)](#) was included in the evaluation. TITAN is also a spatially emphasized quality control method including various QC tests like plausibility, buddy and climatological tests. The set of tests and adjustment of some significant parameters are user definable. Here, TITAN was used to qualify the same set of the NetAtmo data that was run through the kriging and clustering methods without any adjustment of the settings to the version that is freely available in the development environment (<https://github.com/metno/TITAN>).

The performance of using all stations (i.e. no QC), TITAN, random forest (RF), nearest neighbour (NN) and 2D kriging (OK2D) for the PWS air temperature observations located in Finland is described by mean prediction error in figure 5. The various PWS station sets for

each of the ML methods were created by using different thinning values: 4, 10, 20 and 30. Due to the large number of stations, only values 20 and 30 are used when thinning the lists of all stations. Thus, each QC method in figure 5 has four results with a changing amount of stations left. The fraction of potential PWS stations that were accepted for a certain method and thinning combination is shown at the end of each combination in the brackets. Corresponding figure for the Fennoscandia is shown in figure 6. The corresponding results for air pressure observations excluding TITAN in Fennoscandia is shown in figure 7.

With these evaluation methods, the smallest mean prediction error in most cases is given by the 2D kriging method, although the differences to the other regression methods (RF and NN) are rather small. All QC methods outperform using all stations, that is, using only the thinning method to reduce the number of stations. The differences in mean prediction errors between QC-methods are clearer for smaller areas, i.e. for Finland than for Fennoscandia. Overall, mean prediction errors for the interpolation methods are higher for Fennoscandia than for Finland, suggesting that the interpolation-based approach, at least in its current form, is better suited for analyzing smaller geographical areas. The reason for this is still unclear. One hypothesis could be that the regression methods as they are now work better in smaller regions as they do not have to model such complex phenomena at the same time. The method was also developed with smaller regions (e.g. Uusimaa), and only tested with the entire Fennoscandia at the end of the project.

The effect of the used value for the thinning parameter is rather small.

Unfortunately, the clustering method is not included in the performance evaluation because of some unresolved problems with the evaluation. If the problem can be solved, the results can be reported as part of the final report or as an annex in this report.

Figure 5. Mean prediction errors of all stations, TITAN, random forest (RF), nearest neighbor (NN) and 2D kriging (OK2D) for the air temperature observations of NetAtmo stations located in Finland. The performance of each QC method is shown with four thinning options (4, 10, 20, 30)

Figure 6. Mean prediction errors of all stations, TITAN, random forest (RF), nearest neighbor (NN) and 2D kriging (OK2D) for the air temperature observations of NetAtmo stations located in Fennoscandia. The performance of QC each method is shown with four thinning options (4, 10, 20, 30)

Figure 7. Mean prediction errors of all stations, random forest (RF), nearest neighbor (NN) and 2D kriging (OK2D) for the air pressure observations of NetAtmo stations located in Fennoscandia. The performance of each QC method is shown with four thinning options (4, 10, 20, 30).

Present state and development needs

Within the iOBS project, advanced QC-methods for CWS and PWS observations were developed. The outcomes of the work are promising but further studies and development is needed to optimize the methods and investigate if those are realistically capable to work operationally. The following chapters describe the open questions and development needs of the methods.

Spatial QC analysis method, DLMQC

DLMQC was developed to detect slowly evolving drifting of air temperature observations of CWSs. Air temperature was chosen as a parameter because of a known drifting case in Finland. Because of the statistical character of the method, it requires a long reliable observation history and thus, the DLMQC method is not optimal for example for the PWS observations. Within the project, the method managed to handle monthly air temperature values. The decomposed components (trend, cyclic and residual) of the dynamic linear model seemed to be too noisy to find clear shifting behaviour for the shorter observation periods than a month.

In the future, the method could be studied for other parameters, like air pressure. In addition, it would be interesting to investigate further the possibilities to modify the method to be able to handle shorter observation periods.

Automatic adaptive range test

Automatic adaptive range test was studied further based on the method already operational at the FMI. The idea of the method is to create thresholds for the air temperature based on rather longer than shorter observation history of maximum and minimum values of air temperature. The mathematical basis is in generalized extreme-value function. The method was tested also for the air pressure. However, thresholds created seemed not to add any value to the already available ones because of the rather loose thresholds.

Within the project, the operational threshold test was updated at the FMI based on the studies of the iOBS project. Automatic yearly update of the thresholds was implemented. In addition, stations with shorter observation history now use thresholds of chosen neighboring stations as test ranges and station based update of the thresholds was enabled by building a user interface for the manual update of the station thresholds.

In the future, the neighboring stations should be included in the method as additional information for the generalized extreme value function. This would require definition of e.g. the allowed distance and elevation difference between stations as well as the information about the proximity of the water near the stations. In addition, more investigations could be done to see the possibility to use the algorithm to create thresholds for the other parameters than air temperature. In these cases various observation distributions should be taken into account.

Spatial consistency of PWS with CWS, Kriging

The capability of a kriging method based on the spatial consistency between PWS and CWS network to qualify air pressure and temperature observations of PWSs was studied. Based on the consistency between the observation field created by CWS based interpolation and PWS observations, the PWS network was filtered to include only the stations that responded to the requirements set by the method parameters. The method was run once per day to create the list of accepted stations for the data assimilation. The running cycle was chosen based on the duration to run the algorithm and the whole data pipeline. The package handled the whole area, e.g. Finland or Fennoscandia, within the one run of the algorithm.

The next step to be taken would be to optimize the method for shorter running cycles if possible. For example, the running cycle of training data for the method was not optimized within the project. In addition, closer studies on the benefits of the 2D kriging, RF and NN methods could be considered as 2D kriging is computationally heavier than RF and NN. The effect of running 2D kriging for the small areas instead of the whole area from where data is available could also be explored. The method includes parameters that enable adjustment of the output results. Systematic investigation of the influence of parameter values on the outcome of the algorithm would give information about usability of the method for e.g. various user needs. Further testing of the method with the extended area of the data and

extended data sources would be interesting to show the flexibility of the 2D kriging algorithm. This also demands rethinking of the training and testing datasets to be used and how the choosing of those influence the outputs.

Spatial and observation-space density-based clustering

The NetAtmoQC package was developed within iOBS WP2 to test the use of unsupervised machine learning density-based clustering in the quality control of observations from NetAtmo stations. The code defines a generalised distance matrix between reported observations, taking into account not only spatial coordinates, but all reported parameters with separate, customisable weights assigned to them. The calculated distance matrix is then passed to the selected clustering algorithm. Such an approach provides a way to (i) group together similar observations provided by stations located in geographically close regions and (ii) identify possible inconsistent observations (i.e., those that are not found to be members of any cluster).

The code has been tested with a limited amount of data available for the project, and the results seem promising, with most clear outlier observations successfully spotted. Many optimisations have been implemented to handle large amounts of data, including, but not limited to, efficient use of memory by using sparse matrices, use of spatial subdomains to reduce the number of distances calculated, as well as single-host and MPI parallelism.

From a technical point of view, further work on the parallelisation strategies could lead to more performance gains. Robustness against crashes could also be improved by implementing saved checkpoints, such that runs wouldn't need to be restarted from scratch should failures occur. Most of the critical parts of the code have been covered by unit tests, but adding more tests for increased code coverage would be beneficial.

Further testing with extended data would be beneficial in future developments. For benchmarking of the implemented methods, it would be interesting to adapt the code to ingest data from trusted/well-established sources (e.g. data from trusted synop stations), introducing random errors to these and asserting that such errors would be flagged. The implemented custom metrics itself could also be further studied. The default used weights, for instance, have been set heuristically in order to minimise the number of outlier observations wrongly labelled as trustworthy. One could even envision using machine learning to define the best values for such weights. But testing different functional forms for the metrics would also be desirable. Only a limited number of clustering and outlier removal methods have been implemented and tested, given the short-term nature of the project. Exploring more such methods and strategies certainly has potential to lead to better results with better usage of computational resources.